

Investigations on Intercalation Mechanism of Potassium Ion in Layered $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$

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Abstract:

Li-ion batteries (LIBs) established as ubiquitous power source, especially in last three decades. LIBs may suffers from rarity and uneven distribution of resources, which limits their large scale applications. As alternative, potassium ion battery seize the attention of the scientific community due to high negative potential (-2.93V vs SHE) of the cathode materials next to Li-ion and almost having equal abundance like the Na-ion. Very recently, interesting result based on K-ion intercalating behavior of P2-type Na_xCoO_2 was demonstrated by sada et al., (1). However, research on layered oxide electrodes for K-ion battery is in an embryonic phase (2). In our work, we have investigated K-ion intercalation performance of layered $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ for the first time. The $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ was synthesized by conventional solid-state technique using NaNO_3 and MnCO_3 as precursors salts (3). Formation of triclinic symmetry P-1 with $[\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7]_{2-\infty}$ layers fashioned with edge sharing octahedral of MnO_6 was confirmed from X-ray Diffraction and refined the structure using GSAS software. The systematic electrochemical studies were carried out by assembling a K-ion half-cell with K-metal as anode and $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ as active material in 0.8 M KPF_6 non-aqueous electrolyte. The fully K-ion intercalated structure $\text{Na}_{2-x}\text{K}_x\text{Mn}_2\text{O}_7$ ($x=2$) was delivered a reversible capacity of $\sim 108 \text{ mA h g}^{-1}$ and good rate performance with columbic efficiency of ~ 95 %. The Ex-situ XRD measurements confirmed the phase transition and K-ion (de)intercalation. The detailed intercalation mechanism in lamellar type of $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$ will be discussed.

Keywords: $\text{Na}_2\text{Mn}_3\text{O}_7$, Potassium-ion battery, Capacity, Cathode, layered structure.

References:

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